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Sociolinguistic Variation Resulting from TV Commercials' Code-Switched/Code-Mixed Linguistic Landscape: A Study from ESL Perspective

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Abstract

This exploratory study investigates and analyzes the extent of code-mixing and code-switching use in various Pakistani TV commercials. The sample frame was set from the TV commercials broadcasted on widely seen channels such as PTV, ARY Digital, HUM TV, and GEO TV. It aims to trace the implications of this fascinating and fast-emerging phenomenon for English as a Second Language (ESL) learners. This scrutiny has used a two-layered descriptive, sequential quantitative research design. Thirty-two commercials aired between 2000 and 2023 were selected in the first layer. The data were transcribed and evaluated to determine the frequency of code-mixing and code-switching for commercial applications. In the second layer, a questionnaire was distributed to 120 students and evaluated to ascertain the influence of code-mixing/code-switching on ESL learners. The sample population was selected from Punjab University, GC Women University Sialkot, and Government Murray College. The study results indicate various forms of code-mixing and code-switching are common in commercials. English has influenced Urdu for various reasons, including fashion, practicality, and technical progress. Commercials are devised artistically and strategically for a planned and peculiar impact on the audience. Besides enthralling them, it also affects their linguistic behaviors, choices and variation styles. In light of the participants' feedback, to preserve the unique national identity of Pakistan, this study proposes incorporating Urdu flavors and reducing the excessive usage of English in Pakistani TV advertisements. Further research is necessary to address this important socio-cognitive issue in sociolinguistics and English Language Teaching (ELT).

Keywords: *Sociolinguistic Variation; Electronic media; Code-Switching; Code-Mixing; ESL Learners*

Introduction

Sociolinguistic variation concentrates on how language varies due to the changes in the communities of speakers. It focuses on interactions between social aspects and linguistic structures. Today, electronic media is vital for manipulating people's mentalities and linguistic and behavioral patterns. The language of media significantly influences the language utilized by audiences, readers, or listeners. Throughout the world, humans use multiple languages to communicate with one another for effective and peaceful co-existence. Therefore, code-switching and code-mixing are broadly observed trends in bilingual and multilingual communities in the

modern world for obvious socio-political factors. Code-switching is a linguistic term that refers to using more than one language or variety in conversations. Depending on the target audience, the situation, and the goal, it shifts between two or more languages. Code-switching is the juxtaposition within the same speech exchange of passages belonging to two grammatical systems or subsystems (Nilep, 2006).

According to Poplack (1980), three code-switching types are grounded in the context where language shift occurs. These include intra-sentential, inter-sentential, and tag switching. Intra-sentential switching occurs within the confines of a sentence or a clause. It is restricted to blending one language into the other at the word or phrase level. In comparison, inter-sentential switching occurs at the boundary of sentences or clauses. When speaking in language A, tag-switching entails utilizing a tag or tag question from language B.

Code-mixing is another trend correlated with code-switching. It generally happens when a conversant flips between the two languages within a single speech. It may incorporate phonology, morphology, grammatical structures, or lexical items at different linguistic levels. Hudson described code-mixing as a situation where two fluent bilinguals change their language without any change in the situation. It is also crucial to briefly elaborate on ESL (English as a Second Language). Such learners are described as students whose primary language is other than English and who need supplementary English language assistance to develop reading, writing, listening, and speaking skills (Abdoulaye, 2019).

Background:

In this era of technology, communication has become more effortless as communication tools are easily accessible. Human communication began with gestures, symbols, and sounds developed in different languages and is now associated with technological equipment like radio, TV, Internet, and mobile phones. The traditional idea of language as a communication tool has evolved due to the rapid changes in the current world. Language is crucial in every aspect of our lives. It delivers messages and has become our identity, an expression, and a way for socialization. It is the medium through which the rituals and traditions of society are transmitted to future generations. Language and society are intimately unified and cannot be kept apart as each substantially impacts the other. There are thousands of languages worldwide, and they influence each other. When they are in contact, it naturally leads to language variation.

Code-switching and Code-mixing are the consequent phenomena of language contact and a prominent feature of bilingual or multilingual societies to make communication efficient and smooth. The history of bilingualism in the Indian subcontinent dates back to the colonial era when the British introduced English as a

language of progress, which people were compelled to adopt. Such a language culture, where social class profoundly influences linguistic behaviors and practices, has been adopted by Urdu speakers. English is an international language and is regarded as a language of prestige. Therefore, people conceitedly use English as their national language as it associates them with the affluent. Media speaks people's language and affects their language behaviors. The media portrays a social transformation in Pakistan where social intensity and values are associated with wealthy individuals who are educated and speak a sophisticated language. This transformation is visible in marketing messages in general and in commercials in particular. Thus, it is important to analyze the relationship between the language landscape of Pakistan and television advertisements in light of changing patterns.

Scope and Significance of the Study

TV commercials are an extremely alluring way of disseminating information. The current study examines English code-switching and code-mixing in Pakistani TV commercials because these language techniques are repeated and circulated daily to provoke the audience. As a result, they may not only influence viewers but also reflect their linguistic preferences. The audience inevitably adopts suggested products and linguistic patterns. All news channels aim to improve ratings by increasing their news intrigue and appeal through various means. The use of code-switching and code-mixing enhances the artistic value of language. Thus, it is worthwhile to identify to what extent English code-mixing/code-switching is used in Pakistani TV Commercials, its role in the language of commercials, and its impacts on ESL learners.

Limitations and Delimitations of Study:

The current study was limited to 32 commercials aired on Pakistani TV channels such as PTV, HUM TV, ARY Digital, and GEO TV between 2000 and 2023. Moreover, the sample population was 120 taken from Government College Women University Sialkot, Punjab University, and Murray College Sialkot. The sample ages ranged from 18 to 25 years. Unlike scholars, who can dedicate numerous years to research a single topic, the researchers in this study had limited time. This exploration was conducted in a specific setting within a short period. Although the scope of this research is limited to these specifications, as academic research, the sample taken meets the requirement concerning exploring the depth of the issue. It offers food for thought for future researchers. This research examined the frequency of code-mixing/code-switching in 32 Pakistani TV commercials, its impact on ESL learners, and its role in the advertising agenda.

Statement of the Problem:

The information revolution in digital media has transformed the world into a global village. Pakistan, a growing nation with numerous societal, economic, diplomatic, and defense concerns, is not isolated from the media world. The regular usage of English with Urdu is noticeable in daily life and is also evident in broadcasting because it has become a symbol of modernism. Advertising significantly impacts customers' purchasing decisions, which means that how advertisements are presented plays a crucial role in influencing consumer behavior. People pay close attention when commercials are appealing and pleasant. Besides colorful presentations, enthralling sounds, and imaging, code-switched/code-mixed language plays a key role. Therefore, this study explores and analyzes the degree to which English has influenced the language of Pakistani TV commercials over the past years and its impact on ESL learners.

Aim and Objectives

We have conducted this study to examine code-mixing and code-switching in Pakistani TV commercials broadcasted on popular channels. We aim to assess the impact of this linguistic phenomenon on individuals learning English as a second language. To achieve this research goal, we have established the following objectives:

- First, it highlights how frequently Pakistani TV commercials swap between and blend Urdu and English codes.
- Second, this study examines how ESL students are affected by English code-switching and code-mixing.
- Third, this study explores the role of code-switched/code-mixed languages in advertising agendas.

Research Questions

1. What is the frequency of code-mixing/code-switching in Pakistani TV commercials?
2. How does TV commercial code-switching/code-mixing affect ESL learners?
3. How does a code-switched/code-mixed language evoke viewers' desire to buy products and play a major role in advertising agendas?

Literature Review

The subject of code-switching and code-mixing is not new in the field of research. It has been the subject of several investigations in various languages and contexts, including the media, the workplace, advertisements, workbooks, academic texts, texting, and electronic communication. It is also one of the manifest linguistic concerns of bilingual and multilingual communities. It has been the goal of many

academics to define code-switching and code-mixing. According to Hymes (2003), code-switching indicates the alternative usage of two or more languages, variants of a language, or even speech styles. It is the pre-eminently bilingual mode of interaction categorized by frequent shifts from one language to the other in the flow of natural conversation. There are generally three types of code-switching: tag switching, inter-sentential, and intra-sentential. Tag switching encloses a tag from one language to a different one. For example, *kiu ro rahi ho?* What happened? Inter-sentential switching occurs when the language switch is made at sentence boundaries. For example, *Ayesha buhat achi larki hai*, she obeys her parents. In intra-sentential switching, the speaker shifts language within a sentence. "I like her *kiu k wo buhat honest hai.*"

Hammink (2000) defines code-mixing as swapping at the word, clause, and phrase level if no morphological variation happens. It deliberately merges characteristics of two or more languages without an associated topic change. Some scholars use these terms synonymously, but others view the two conspicuously. Bokamba (1988) differentiates the two by stressing that code-switching occurs at the inter-sentential while code-mixing occurs at the intra-sentential level. In Pakistan, bilingualism has been the impetus for researching the fascinating phenomenon of code-switching and code-mixing. The status and use of the native/national language in Pakistan are constantly changing. Sameen et al. (2021) quite pertinently put it,

Code-switching is a popular tool of choice when it comes to teaching in Pakistan. It is because most of the education in Pakistan is delivered in English, a foreign language to all. Modern-day learners are uncomfortable with the language and lack the confidence to adapt to it. The language has become a stigma in the average modern-day Pakistani society. The continuous reinforcement of this language in academia, coupled with the stigma that the language has become, leads to a lack of confidence in students, so much so that they get demotivated in learning. (P-111)

A Pakistani child grabs Urdu at home and learns his mother tongue. As he ages, he must learn English for academic and professional needs. In the current scenario, English increasingly dominates our discourse. English is used alongside Urdu in both formal and informal settings. It is not only a linguistic spectacle, but we can also notice this practice in the language of media. The term "media" refers to all traditional forms of communication, including radio, television, print media, and other electronic/digital channels. Media is crucial in bringing variation in the world's lifestyles, behaviours, and language patterns (Johnson, 2007). In this era of technology, nobody can deny the importance and effectiveness of media. It represents the society and sociocultural practices of a particular nation.

The media significantly impacts the cultural and psychological state of people in Pakistan. Zahoor A. et al. (2020) found out, "The young generation expresses its political views freely on Social Networking Sites. Whatever people encounter on social media builds up their linguistic cognition and impacts it in various ways" (p. 78). The Pakistani television industry frequently incorporates the English language, making it the subject of research scrutiny. In 2013, 200 respondents from various Pakistani cities were used in a large-scale study to examine whether the media can alter Pakistanis' attitudes and opinions. The results indicate that social media has an excessively negative impact that, if not managed properly, will injure the future of Pakistani students (Khan, 2013). Kotler (2003) has analyzed the nature of marketing messages regarding TV commercials. He observes that advertising messages are deliberately made well-designed, more inventive, compelling, and pleasing to consumers to obtain and keep attention.

Moreover, creative and captivating language use in TV commercials is crucial to gaining viewers' attention (Kotler, 2003). Hashim (2010) researched the advertisements of six different languages and found that language mixing is universal. English is commonly the 'mixed' language and is often code-mixed with local languages to fill the advertising industry's demand for creativity and innovation in advertisements. After a semantic analysis of Pakistani advertisements over a month, Mehwish (2015) discovered linguistic techniques to boost the charismatic appeal. Using twenty students, Mushtaq (2012) investigated the impact of code-mixing on Pakistani commercial viewers. The results signify that code-mixing is prevalent in commercials and has a good effect on the spectators because it assists in effectively communicating the message.

Aalia (2014) concludes that the language of advertisements replicates a revolution in linguistic preferences and practices of Pakistani customers after analyzing the social aspects of code-switching in 12 Pakistani TV advertisements of health care and beauty products. In Pakistan, the definition of beauty for both men and women evolves on a daily basis. It is closely associated with the practice of advanced and blended language. The language of advertisements discloses the wishes of the lower-middle class to join the higher class by following brand-new fashions of beauty (Khan, 2014). Another research also aimed to do a stylistic analysis of the TV ads broadcasted in Pakistan based on code-mixing and code-switching. The results show that Urdu has been affected by English for many reasons: style, ease, and technical evolutions (Riaz, 2019). Furthermore, Amjad (2020) also researched ten media advertisements to highlight the effect of the English language and how multilingual societies embraced different ways to simultaneously make the use of distinct languages possible.

Herman (2022) analyzed the prevalence and causes of code mixing in TV ads, particularly among young people, due to its widespread use in society. Thirty TV advertisements aired between June 1, 2021, and June 6, 2021, were used in the study. Based on the research, two types of code mixing were found: congruent lexicalization and insertion. Harahap (2023) focused on Indonesian tertiary students' perspectives, reasons, and influences regarding code-switched advertisements. Most students thought code-switched advertisements were more persuasive, memorable, and alluring than mono-language ads. Without diminishing the Indonesian language, they were lured to code-switched advertisements' inventiveness, attraction, and clarity. Additionally, the majority of respondents stated that code-switched advertisements had an impact on their decision to make a purchase. This highlights the beneficial effects of code-switched digital advertising on Indonesian tertiary students' preferences and time-spending habits.

The present study addresses a vital research gap in Pakistani TV advertising linguistics. Previous studies, especially the last publication of 2019 in the Pakistani context, primarily examined language variation in commercials by investigating limited advertisements aired from 2011-2015. The present study provides an inclusive and up-to-date analysis covering commercial broadcasts from 2000 to 2023. Examining an extensive period enables us to document the dynamic changes in language usage over time, offering insightful information about current linguistic trends in Pakistani TV advertising. Furthermore, it focuses on the commercials with diverse topics and the potential influence of code-switching and code-mixing on ESL learners that still need to be explored. This expansion of scope and depth not only bridges the prevailing research gap but also ensures the relevance and timeliness of our study in light of changing linguistic usage in Pakistani TV commercials. Thus, this study has evaluated the frequency of code-switching and code-mixing in Pakistani TV commercials from 2000-2023 on different subjects and examined the implication of code-switching/code-mixing on ESL learners. It is important to note that this study is not intended to criticize or diminish any TV channel or product, nor is it aimed at assessing the amount of English or Urdu usage in Pakistani TV commercials. It merely seeks to investigate the frequencies of both linguistic devices to analyze language variation, its impact on ESL Learners, and advertisement plans.

Research Methodology:

Examining "Sociolinguistic Variation Resulting from TV Commercials' Code-Switched/Code-Mixed Linguistic Landscape: A Study from ESL Perspective." involved using descriptive quantitative research design. Textual data analysis was used to observe the frequency of English code-switching and code-mixing in

Pakistani TV commercials. Thirty-two TV commercials broadcasted on PTV, ARY Digital, HUM TV, and GEO TV during 2000-2023 were carefully chosen. They were transcribed, and the frequencies of code-mixing and code-switching were evaluated manually. The text in TV commercials varied in length. They varied in nature and included various products, such as cosmetics, electrical appliances, digital products, telecommunication companies, and edibles like drinks, biscuits, and spices. A questionnaire was also designed to analyze the impact of TV commercial code-switching and code-mixing on ESL (English as a Second Language) learners and their role in advertising agendas.

The questionnaire was conducted from a sample of 120, including Punjab University, GC Women University, and Murray College, Sialkot. A sample of eighty students from GCWUS and Murray College, 40 from each institution, responded to the questionnaire face-to-face, and the remaining 40 participants were recruited through an online survey. The combination of face-to-face and online survey methodologies allowed the researchers to gather data from diverse participants, enhancing the validity and generalizability of the study's findings. The age group of the respondents was from 18-25. The researchers conducted a Cronbach's Alpha test on the collected questionnaire responses. The Cronbach's value of 0.99214 indicated a high level of internal consistency. It ensures the reliability of collected data and supports a thorough analysis of the occurrence and impact of code-mixing and code-switching in Pakistani TV advertising.

Theoretical Framework:

The Variation Theory, a solid theoretical framework with linguistic roots, has been employed in this study to explore the sociolinguistic landscape within Pakistani TV commercials. It provides a comprehensive viewpoint for analyzing the prevalence and implication of code-mixing and code-switching, particularly between Urdu and English, as observed in advertising. The researchers decoded the motivations underlying these linguistic variations by adopting this theory. They revealed the impact of various elements, such as fashion trends, pragmatism, and technological advances in language choices. Additionally, it has shed light on the complex social and psychological aspects of code-switching and code-mixing, emphasizing how these linguistic techniques support the perception of the English language as the source of prestige and appeal. This research underlines the critical requirement for linguistic equilibrium in Pakistani TV advertising under the purview of this theoretical framework. The study supports the thoughtful insertion of Urdu linguistic features to maintain Pakistan's rich national identity while prudently reducing the overuse of English to achieve a healthy linguistic balance that respects the country's cultural legacy and linguistic diversity.

Data Analysis and Findings:

Textual data analysis:

Thirty-two Pakistani TV commercials aired on PTV, ARY Digital, HUM TV, and GEO TV during 2000-2023 were selected and transcribed. All English words used in the data were underlined and calculated for data analysis. The repeated English words in any TV commercial have yet to be integrated. Code-mixing is taken as the words and phrases of the English language used in the commercials, and code-switching is taken as the entire sentences of English. The brand names, such as Oreo, Ufone, Fanta, Dew, Care, PEPSI, and Tapal, have frequently been used in many commercials. The total number of words is counted in the commercials, and then the code-switched words are calculated cautiously. The mathematical formula of percentage has been used for checking the frequencies.

Figure 1: Increasing trend of English in Commercials 2000-2012

Figure 1 illustrates the frequency of English and Urdu use in Pakistani TV advertisements between 2000 and 2012. The frequency of English words in the first four commercials (C1-C4) between 2000 and 2002 ranged from 03 to 08, whereas the frequency of Urdu words ranged from 15 to 31. The frequency of English words in the next four commercials (C5-C8) between 2003 and 2005 ranged from 08 to 16, whereas the frequency of Urdu words ranged from 30 to 40. The frequency of English words in the next four commercials (C9-C12) between 2006 and 2008 ranged from 09 to 20, whereas the frequency of Urdu words ranged from 15 to 50. The frequency of English words in the next four commercials (C13-C16) between 2009 and 2011 ranged from 25 to 36, while the frequency of Urdu words ranged from 53 to 60. Overall, we can see a clear upward trend in the number of English words used in 16 Pakistani TV commercials from 2000 to 2012.

Figure 2: Increasing trend of English in Commercials 2013-2023

Figure. 2 demonstrates the frequency of English and Urdu in Pakistani TV commercials between 2013 and 2023. The frequency of English words in the first four commercials (C1-C4) between 2013 and 2015 ranged from 16 to 35, whereas that of Urdu words ranged from 25 to 45. The frequency of English words in the next four commercials (C5-C8) between 2016 and 2018 ranged from 20 to 38, whereas the frequency of Urdu words ranged from 25 to 53. The frequency of English words in the next four commercials (C9-C12) between 2019 and 2021 ranged from 22 to 45, whereas the frequency of Urdu words ranged from 25 to 55. The frequency of English words in the next four commercials (C13-C16) between 2022 and 2023 ranged from 33 to 50, while the frequency of Urdu words ranged from 50 to 60. Overall, we noticed a palpable increasing tendency in the number of English words used in 16 Pakistani TV commercials from 2013 to 2023.

Table 1: The frequency of code-switched and code-mixed words

Number of Channels	04
Number of Commercials	32
Years of Commercials	2000-2023
Total words in the Commercials	1991
Number of code-switched and code-mixed words	797
Percentage of code-switched and code-mixed words	40.03%

The findings given in the above table show that from thirty-two TV commercials selected from four channels from 2000 to 2023, the total number of words in the commercials was 1991. The next row shows the figure of words used as code-switched/code-mixed words, which are 797 in total. In the last row, the percentage calculated from the number of code-switched/code-mixed words and the total number of words is 40.03%.

Figure 3: Comparative Analysis of English and Urdu Words in Pakistani TV Commercials between 2000-2012 and 2013-2023

Data Analysis: Questionnaire

This paper is a descriptive quantitative study with a questionnaire as the data collection tool to gather data from 120 respondents. It had 16 questions.

Figure 4

Do you think that mixing languages has a role to play in Pakistani TV commercials?

Figure 5

Do you pay close attention to commercials?

Figure 6

How many hours do you spend watching television in a week?

The results have revealed that 25% watch television from 6-10 hours, 15% watch it from 14-18 hours, 23% watch it very untimely, and 37% watch it rarely. The gathered information shows that television is viewed with great interest, so people also watch the commercials. 24% agreed that they observe the ads keenly, 10% responded as neutral, 34% watch them very often, and 33% answered that they do not see them at all. It implies that 24% of people who very keenly observe ads take influence out of them. 58% agree that mixing languages has played a starring role in the commercials, 20% strongly agree on it, 15% are neutral, 5% disagree with the notion, and 2% strongly disagree that it has a role to play.

Figure 7

How much the concept of intermixing language is harmful to Urdu as a language?

Figure 8

Does the concept of intermixing languages make advertisements entertaining?

Figure 9

Does the concept of intermixing languages make advertisements more understandable?

The findings reveal that people appreciate linguistic diversity and have embraced English-dominant culture. When asked if mixing languages harms Urdu, 33% of respondents said "YES, 27% strongly agreed, 25% were neutral, 10% disagreed, and 5% of the sample strongly disagreed. The statistics reveal that 22% of the sample agreed that intermixing languages makes commercials pleasant, 27% strongly agreed, 28% were neutral, 20% disagreed, and 3% strongly disagreed. 35% agreed that intermixing languages makes commercials understandable, and 25%

strongly agreed. 22% of the participants responded neutral, 13% disagreed, and 5% strongly disagreed.

Figure 10

Do you agree that code-switching has become necessary for a TV commercial?

Figure 11

Does code switching have an impact on the viewer's psychology?

Figure 12

The better the catchy words, the better the influence it has, how much do you agree?

The results showed that 47% of the participants agreed that code-switching had become a necessary TV commercial, 15% strongly agreed, and 15% were neutral. 20% disagreed that code-switching had become as essential as choosing a good idea for a commercial, and 3% of the total sample strongly disagreed. 57% agreed that code-switching affects the viewer's psyche, 17% strongly agreed, 15% remained neutral, 8% disagreed, and 3% strongly disagreed. 50% of the respondents agreed, 30% strongly agreed, 12% remained neutral, 8% disagreed, and no respondent strongly disagreed that the more appealing words have a more enticing effect.

Figure 13

Does the use of code-switching/code-mixing is increasing among advertisements?

Figure 14

Does Code Switching/code mixing in advertisements boost the desire to purchase the product?

Figure 15

How much do you agree that commercials have a different effect on different age groups?

The results indicate that 55% of the respondents agree that code-switching is an increasing trend among TV commercials, 30% strongly agreed, 5% were indecisive, and 10% disagreed. 40% agreed that code-switching boosts the desire to purchase the product, 22% strongly agreed that 20% remained neutral, 18% disagreed with this statement, and 0% strongly disagreed. 50% agreed that commercials had a different effect on different age groups, 20% strongly agreed, 17% remained indecisive, 10% disagreed, and 3% strongly disagreed.

Figure 16

Are you of the opinion that without code switching/code mixing, commercials will be less effective?

Figure 17

Do you believe that mixing English and Urdu in TV advertising is beneficial?

The findings reveal that 45% of the participants agree that without code-switching/code-mixing, commercials will be less effective, 17% strongly agree, 12% are neutral, 18% disagree, and 8% strongly disagree. 7% responded neutrally, 20% disagreed, and 3% strongly disagreed. 50% agreed that mixing English and Urdu is beneficial in TV commercials, 20% strongly agreed, 7% responded neutral, 20% disagreed, and 2% strongly disagreed.

Figure 18

Do you think that Code-switching/code mixing plays a significant role for goods in raising their market value?

Figure 19

Do you believe that code-switching/code mixing has become a popular trend in Pakistani TV commercials?

The above figure indicates that 52% of the participants agree that code-switching/code-mixing plays a significant role in raising their market value; 30% strongly agreed, 2% responded as neutral, 13% disagreed, and 3% strongly disagreed. 32% of participants agreed that code-switching/code-mixing had become a popular trend in Pakistani TV commercials, 37% strongly agreed, 13% responded as neutral, 13% disagreed, and 5% strongly disagreed. The research was to unravel how the Urdu language is impacted by English code-switching/code-mixing. The results proved that it significantly affects Pakistan's national language and intensely impacts ESL learners.

Discussion:

The study revealed compelling results, leading to a comprehensive discussion of three main research questions exploring how language works in Pakistani TV advertisements. Addressing the first research question, which investigates the frequency of code-mixing and code-switching in Pakistani TV commercials, the findings revealed that about 40.03% of the words in Pakistani TV advertisements involved mixing languages, emphasizing a deliberate and strategic use of language diversity in advertising. This change over time advocates a shift in marketing strategies, possibly influenced by pricing strategies, fashion trends, and technical progressions. This finding underscores a pervasive linguistic phenomenon in the advertising landscape.

The second research question considered the influence of code-mixing and code-switching on ESL learners. 58% of respondents agree that linguistic variety in advertisements has a good impact, indicating a receptive attitude among ESL learners. However, 33% expressed concerns about potential harm to Urdu due to linguistic mixing. This dual response highlights the intricate nature of language

dynamics among ESL learners, where they appreciate diversity but also worry about its impact on their native language.

The third question investigated how code-mixing and code-switching shaped viewer desires and influenced advertising agendas. The findings showed a substantial psychological impact, with 57% of respondents believing that code-mixing and code-switching influenced viewers' attention. Additionally, 47% recognized the pivotal role of language mixing in enhancing the attractiveness of TV ads, aligning with existing literature on the strategic use of language to amplify advertising effectiveness.

The research highlights the rampant utilization of code-mixing and code-switching in Pakistani television ads, emphasizing its strategic importance in advertising. The study supports the Variety Hypothesis, advocating for the judicious incorporation of Urdu elements. Thus, a balanced approach to language use is essential to preserve Urdu's distinctiveness while appreciating the influence of English. The present study contributes valuable insights, addresses existing literature gaps, and emphasizes the ongoing need for research to navigate evolving language dynamics. Establishing clear language-use guidelines is crucial for maintaining cultural diversity and linguistic equilibrium.

Conclusion

Accumulated records and evaluations reveal that Urdu is developing through code-switching and code-mixing. We can also find a few illustrations of word manipulation for the intent of affluence and modernity. The language of Pakistani TV commercials has changed considerably because of English code-switching/code-mixing, which greatly impacts English as a Second Language (ESL) learners. The blending boundaries between Urdu and English reveal the attitudes of both language speakers. Several Urdu words are replaced with English words to make the message more attractive and engaging even if their Urdu equivalents are available. The results indicate that people use code-mixing and code-switching not only for accuracy and eloquence but also because they are enthralled by English, regarding it as the language of prestige. It plays a vibrant role in boosting the temptation of products because it makes commercials catchier and more glamorous. The advertising messages are adroitly designed in TV commercials, with a high profile of contributors and exaggerated settings to express that a certain product brings comfort, beauty, and social affluence. This bilingual linguistic activity creates a new language culture and makes us aware that a language needs to be dynamic enough to incorporate foreign language structures. However, setting firm boundaries for using English in Pakistani TV commercials is important to preserve Urdu's unique identity.

Suggestions and Recommendations:

The following are some suggestions for further research.

- The study can be conducted on a large sample size and diverse regions.
- Research can be conducted with a sample of different age groups and didactic levels.
- Research can be organized exclusively on product names or commercial slogans.

Even though languages evolve instinctively and manipulate one another, it is crucial to analyze the extent to which these variations may be obliged. Therefore, this study has explored the impact of English on Pakistani TV commercials from 2000 to 2023 and its influence on English as a second language (ESL) learners.

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